

Growth of Sb_2Se_3 thin films by selenization of RF sputtered binary precursors

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Abstract

In this work we developed a method to grow Sb_2Se_3 thin films with a potential use as absorber layers in solar cell structures. The films were grown on top of soda-lime glass, Mo coated soda-lime glass and Si substrates. The Sb-Se precursor's films were deposited by RF magnetron sputtering and then annealed with an H_2Se gas flow. Different annealing temperatures were tested and analyzed. Compositional and morphological analyses are performed by Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy and Scanning Electron Microscopy, respectively. Phase identification and structural characterization are done by X-ray Diffraction and Dispersive Raman Spectroscopy showing that Sb_2Se_3 is the dominant phase with an orthorhombic crystalline structure. Traces of rhombohedral and amorphous Se secondary phases are also observed supported by their Se-rich compositions. Spectrophotometry measurements allowed to extract a direct bandgap with a value close to 1.06 eV. Photoluminescence spectroscopy shows a broad shoulder at 0.85 eV for samples selenized at lower temperatures and an intense peak at 0.75 eV for the sample selenized at higher temperatures. Electrical characterization shows low free hole concentrations and mobilities. At low temperatures, the analysed samples show that nearest neighbour hopping is the dominant mechanism for the electronic transport. A discussion on the properties that need to be improved in order that these films can be used in thin film solar cells is done.

Keywords: Sb_2Se_3 , thin film, Raman, XRD.

1. Introduction

It is well known that one way of creating an environmentally friendly energy production momentum, which allows mitigating the effects of climate change, is closely linked to the commercial relevance of renewable energy production systems. Photovoltaic technology can play an important role in this field. Currently dominated by Si-based technology, it has some drawbacks that prevent a greater market presence. High energy payback time, low industrial production rate and, high values of initial investment for a production facilities, among others, are constraints to a higher PV share in the energy production systems in most countries. Due to monolithic integration, lower energy processes and lower material demand, thin film technology presents good arguments to overcome Si technology. CIGS

and CdTe based PV cells are currently the most powerful representatives of thin film technology on the market. However, the solar cells based on these materials present problems related to the scarcity and toxicity of some elements that compose them. Alternative materials are currently being studied, such like $\text{Cu}_2\text{ZnSn}(\text{S},\text{Se})_4$, to be applied as absorber layer in the solar cell structure. But due to its intrinsic complex pentanary structure and restricted growth conditions some difficulties have been encountered. These facts have prevented the production of devices with efficiencies compatible with their commercialization.

Antimony selenide, Sb_2Se_3 , is a semiconductor material that belongs to the $A_m^V B_n^{VI}$ group, crystallizing in an orthorhombic configuration of the Pnma (62) space group [1]. The first research was published in the 50 s, where the isomorphism of antimony selenide to antimony sulfide, Sb_2S_3 , is investigated and the structural parameters of Sb_2Se_3 are described [2]. Later, this data was confirmed by other research groups [3, 4], as shown in table 1. As a current standard, the crystal lattice parameters for Sb_2Se_3 are taken to be $a = 1.16330$ nm, $b = 1.1700$ nm and $c = 0.39850$ nm.

Over the years, as the interest in Sb_2Se_3 became stronger, researchers devoted to the synthesis of this compound have doubled in the recent decade. Studies revealed that this material has excellent electrochemical, opto- and thermo-electric properties.

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lattices param.	ref. [1]	ref. [2]	ref. [3]
a (nm)	1.168	1.171	1.17938
b (nm)	1.158	1.162	1.16478
c (nm)	0.398	0.396	0.39858

Table 1: Comparison of the literature data on the Sb_2Se_3 cell dimensions.

39 Sb_2Se_3 exhibits a direct band-gap between 1.04 - 1.3 eV and optical absorption coefficient higher than 10^5 cm^{-1} in the visible region [5], carrier mobility $\approx 10 \text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$ for minority carriers and, based on the transient absorption spectroscopy, a carrier lifetime $\approx 60 \text{ ns}$ [6]. In addition, recently it has been discovered that Sb_2Se_3 shows an extremely large magnetoresistance [30]. Based on the electrochemical properties, this material has been suggested as an anode material for lithium-ion batteries [8] and hydrogen storage materials [9]. Optoelectronic properties of the material have found applications in optical recording material [10, 11], in thermoelectric devices [12], solar cells and photoelectrochemical cells [13]. At the moment, the best power conversion efficiency value for a Sb_2Se_3 based thin film solar cell with a substrate/FTO/ZnO/ Sb_2Se_3 /Au structure configuration is 5.93 % [14]. However, theoretically calculated gaps with the ideal Shockley-Queisser value predicted that the efficiency of a solar cells based on Sb_2Se_3 can surpass 30 % [15]. In addition to efficiency of solar cells, the critical parameter for development of such devices is the production cost. Here too, Sb_2Se_3 satisfies necessary criteria as antimony and selenium are widespread and rather cheap elements.

Among thin-film growth technology Sb_2Se_3 the most common are thermal evaporation [16–20], spin coating [21], chemical bath deposition [22], ionic layer adsorption and reaction methods [23], spray pyrolysis [24], reactive pulsed laser deposition [8], electrodeposition [25, 26], DC magnetron sputtering [29], resistance-heated floating zone furnace [30], just to mention the most used ones.

In this work, we use a method of growing Sb_2Se_3 thin films based on the deposition of Sb-Se precursors by RF-magnetron sputtering followed by an annealing step in a H_2Se gas atmosphere. The films are prepared on different substrates: SLG, SLG/Mo and Si. We report the effect of the annealing temperatures on the properties of the films. The crystalline structure of the films has been studied by X-ray diffraction and Raman scattering spectroscopy. The characterization of the morphology is done by scanning electron microscopy. Spectrophotometry measurements allowed the study of the optical behaviour of the samples and the determination of the bandgap energies of the compounds. The optoelectronic properties of the samples are also investigated using photoluminescence spectroscopy, Hall effect and electrical resistivity measurements.

2. Experimental Methods

2.1. Preparation of the films

The growth method is based in two stages. The first one refers to the deposition of the binary precursor layer, Sb_xSe_y , by RF magnetron sputtering. The chalcogen incorporation, Se,

the composition adjustment and, the annealing process, which allows the crystalline phase formation, are performed in the second stage. In this work we used three types of substrates: $3 \times 3 \text{ cm}^2$ soda lime glass (SLG), $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ Mo coated SLG and $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ p-Si (100) without removal of the native oxide. The Mo layer thickness is near 350 nm [27]. The samples preparation process begins with the substrate cleaning, with successive ultrasound baths of acetone/alcohol/deionised water. This process ends with the substrate being dried with a N_2 flow. Next, the precursor layers were deposited directly on the different substrates using an Ar atmosphere at an operating pressure of 5×10^{-3} mbar. The Sb_2Se_3 target purity was 99.99%. To avoid target excessive thermal stress or cracking, a low energy density of 0.86 Wcm^2 was used. The precursor film thicknesses of 900 nm was confirmed by dektak profilometry. For the second stage, a rapid thermal furnace system was used. The samples were placed in a susceptor box and submitted to the annealing process depicted in Figure 1. After a quick initial step at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the temperature is raised at a rate of $1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C/s}$ to an isothermal line at the maximum temperature. In this work we tested three different maximum temperatures, 300, 350 and $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. This last step has a duration of 900 s. During ramping and isothermal steps a constant H_2Se gas flow at 200 sccm is used as the Se supplier. After this step the H_2S gas flow stops, the system is forced to undergo a rapid cooling procedure. During this step the furnace chamber is filled with a mixture of N_2 and H_2 .

Figure 1: Annealing temperature profiles for the selenization process with three different tested maximum temperatures (300, 350 and $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The H_2Se gas flux was 200 sccm during the heating ramp and the isothermal line.

2.2. Sample characterization

The composition of the films was analysed by EDS using a Rontec EDS system coupled to a High-resolution NovaNanoSEM 650 SEM system. The accelerating voltage used for the EDS measurements was 30 kV. The same system was used to surface SEM imaging, but with a acceleration voltage of 10 kV. XRD was done in Bragg-Brentano θ - 2θ configuration with a PanAnalytical X Pert PRO MRD system with a CuK_α line of 1.5406 \AA with the following generator settings:

122 current intensity 40 mA and voltage 45 kV. To measure the
 123 precursors' roughnesses and thicknesses a KLA TENCOR P-
 124 16+ contact profilometer was used. Raman scattering experi-
 125 ments were carried out at room temperature (RT) using a Jobin-
 126 Yvon LabRaman HR800 spectrometer equipped with a multi-
 127 channel air cooled (-70 °C) CCD detector, in the backscattering
 128 geometry, and using the 632.8 nm excitation line of a HeNe
 129 laser. The sample surface was focused with an objective of 50x
 130 (N.A=0.50; WD=10.6 mm), and the incident power was varied
 131 from 70 μ W to 790 μ W. The visible-NIR reflectance spectra
 132 were recorded at RT, using a dual-beam spectrometer Lambda
 133 950, (Perkin-Elmer) with a 150 mm diameter Spectralon inte-
 134 grating sphere. The photoluminescence (PL) was measured in
 135 a Bruker Vertex 80v Fourier transform infrared spectrometer
 136 equipped with an InGaAs detector. The samples were inserted
 137 in a He flux cryostat, at 7 K and under He atmosphere. The PL
 138 was excited using the 457.9 nm line from a DPSS laser (CVI
 139 Melles Griot), non-focused on the sample surface. The excita-
 140 tion power value was 200 mW and measured near the entrance
 141 window of the cryostat. The electrical transport properties of
 142 the samples deposited in SLG substrates were investigated by
 143 Hall effect and electrical resistivity. Ohmic gold contacts were
 144 used. Due to the elevated resistivity of the samples, the free hole
 145 concentration and mobilities were only determined at 400 K,
 146 while the resistivity was measured as a function of temperature.

147 3. Results and discussion

148 3.1. Composition and morphology analysis

149 The sample's composition was analysed by EDS. Table 2
 150 shows the results of the composition ratio of the Se over the Sb,
 151 [Se]/[Sb], obtained using this technique. The first row refers
 152 to the as-deposited films, *i e*, the precursors samples before the
 153 selenization process. All samples are Se poor, with ratio values
 154 close to 1.13. These values can be considered the same within
 155 the measurement errors. Additional incorporation of chalcogen
 156 element is observed after the selenization process. In general,
 157 [Se]/[Sb] increases for all temperature profiles and for the three
 158 tested substrates. Nevertheless, a substantial difference can be
 159 observed when the results of the samples with Si substrate are
 160 compared with the SLG and SLG/Mo counterparts. For Si sub-
 161 strates the ratio is close to 1.6 which is close to the stoichiom-
 162 etry value of 1.5. In turn with the other two tested substrates
 163 the amount of detected Se is higher, approximately 1.95. In all
 164 cases the selenization temperature does not seem to have a sig-
 165 nificant effect on the incorporation of additional Se in the films.
 166 At least considering the error margin of the EDS and that it is
 167 semi-quantitative technique. The fact that Si substrate samples
 168 have less Se than the others could be related with its thermal
 169 properties.

170 Surface morphology was investigated using SEM imaging.
 171 Figure 2 shows the surface morphology of the precursor layer
 172 of the sample selenized at 300 °C on SLG. A regular surface
 173 and small grains, with dimensions below 100 nm, can be ob-
 174 served. Figure 3 shows the results for the sample selenized at
 175 300 °C and 400 °C with the three types of substrates. In general,

Max. Selenization temp.	300 °C	350 °C	400 °C
precursors	1.14	1.12	1.14
Substrate - SLG	1.91	2.12	1.93
Substrate - SLG/Mo	1.95	2.11	1.93
Substrate - Si	1.56	1.61	1.62

Table 2: Composition ratio [Se]/[Sb] for precursors and selenized samples at a maximum temperature of 300 °C, 350 °C and 400 °C with three different substrates: SLG, SLG/Mo and Si.

all samples present an increase of the grain size with tempera-
 ture. This increase can be confirmed by the statistical analysis
 presented in Figure 4. Based on previous SEM images, a grain
 contour definition procedure allowed to estimate the grain area
 and determine the area distribution for each case. As example,
 shown in Figure 4, samples selenized at 300 °C and 400 °C
 with SLG/Mo substrates, the peak of the gaussian distribution
 show a clear trend for higher areas, 0.25 \rightarrow 0.50 μ m², when the
 selenization temperature increases. Comparing the results ob-
 served in Figure 3 between the three types of substrates, Si ones
 show a more significant and regular grain increase, which can
 be related with the thermal properties of this type of substrates
 allowing for a different thermal budget or with the increased
 flatness of these substrates compared with SLG and SLG/Mo.
 Small grains can be observed in the sample selenized at 400 °C
 with SLG substrate. Localized EDS measurements, confirmed
 higher Na contents when compared with the average composi-
 tion, which can be explained by the diffusion of this alkali metal
 from the SLG substrates [28]. These grains were not observed
 in the other samples. Sparsely distributed needle like crystal-
 lites can be observed in sample with SLG/Mo. Point EDS mea-
 surements indicated close to stoichiometric Sb₂Se₃ composi-
 tion.

Figure 2: SEM image of a precursor surface sample with SLG substrate.

3.2. XRD characterization

The structural analysis was performed using XRD and Ra-
 man scattering techniques. As shown in Figure 5, Sb₂Se₃
 is the predominant crystalline phase in all the samples. This bi-
 nary compound has a orthorhombic crystalline structure which
 belongs to the Pmna (62) space group. The most important
 reflections occur at 2 θ equal to 16.8°, 23.9°, 27.3° and 34.0°,

Figure 3: Surface SEM micrographs of the samples selenized at 300 °C and 400 °C with the three types of substrates.

Figure 4: Grain area histogram for the samples selenized at 300 °C and 400 °C with SLG/Mo substrates. Inset plot: Grain contour mapping used for area analysis

206 corresponding to the orientation planes (2 0 1), (3 0 1), (3 0 2)
 207 and (4 0 2), respectively [31]. For the tested selenization tempera-
 208 tures, this growth method does not seem to follow columnar
 209 orientation growth, as published in the literature [20]. For
 210 all studied synthesis conditions, the samples follow a planar
 211 growth, shown by the (2 0 1) peak intensity when compared
 212 with the powder pattern and the other peaks. In general, the
 213 sharpness of the peaks attributed to this phase increase with
 214 temperature, meaning that crystallinity increases, as expected.
 215 This behaviour is observed for all three substrate types. Reflec-
 216 tions from secondary phases, such as Sb and MoSe₂, are visible
 217 in samples with SLG/Mo substrates. The crystallization MoSe₂
 218 in a region close to Sb₂Se₃/Mo interface can explain the forma-
 219 tion of Sb phase as MoSe₂ might deprive Sb of Se. In other

220 systems it has been reported that the chalcogenation of the back
 221 contact leads to lack of chalcogen atoms in the absorber layer
 222 [32]. Further tests are needed to confirm this statement. The
 223 diffractograms shown in Figure 5 from sample with SLG/Mo
 224 and Si substrates also present contributions from the substrates
 225 layers. For Mo the reflection is located 40.5° and for Si the
 226 peaks are at 47.5° and 56.1° according to ICDD database [31].
 227 Some artifacts from the Al sample holder are also visible in
 228 these results.

229 It must be highlighted that in literature Sb₂Se₃ space group
 230 is commonly defined using non-standard Pbnm. In this work,
 231 the space group Pnma is adopted. Both Pnma and Pbnm have
 232 the exact same symmetry and belong to the same space group
 233 (No. 62) and are related via a simple transformation [33]. The
 234 differences are evident when comparing orientation planes pre-
 235 viously referred with the ones published [20].

Figure 5: XRD diffractograms of the studied samples with the three different substrate. Blue colored results correspond to maximum selenization temperature of 400 °C, red to 350 °C and black to 300 °C. Colored boxes highlight traces of Sb and MoSe₂ crystalline phases for green and magenta colors, respectively. Contributions from the substrates are also visible, such as Mo and Si. Phase assignment was done using the ICDD database [31].

3.3. Raman scattering results

Raman scattering characterization of the sample selenized at 300 °C with SLG substrate is shown in Figure 6. Two different spots are presented, corresponding to a) a stoichiometric composition region and to b) a Se-rich region of the sample. In the first case, the collected Raman spectrum is in agreement with previously reported literature [37]. According to these authors, the most intense peak at 188 cm⁻¹ is characteristic of Sb-Se

244 stretching mode and it is pointed as an A_g mode. The peak at
 245 150 cm^{-1} can be associated to Sb-Sb bonds, corresponding to
 246 the B_{1g} mode. The vibration modes at 120 and 210 cm^{-1} are
 247 related to Se-Se bonds, which are assigned to A_g modes. The
 248 graph for Se-rich region show additional features located close
 249 to 70 cm^{-1} and, at 102 , 129 and 252 cm^{-1} , which are assigned
 250 to Se with a rhombohedral structure [34]. A small shoulder
 251 close to the 252 cm^{-1} peak is visible indicating that amorphous
 252 Se can also be present in this sample [35]. The power used in
 253 these measurements are maintained as low as possible to avoid
 254 the oxidation of the samples. This issue is addressed in more
 255 detail elsewhere [38]. When comparing these results with the
 256 XRD ones, it is noted that Raman scattering technique can detect
 257 Se excess in the composition. Using this characterization
 258 technique, small amounts of Se in an amorphous and/or in a
 259 crystalline phase can be detected. Although low laser power
 260 has been used, it is very likely that part of the detected crystalline
 261 Se has been formed during the measurement process. Sparse amorphous
 262 and crystalline Se in low quantities are more difficult, if not impossible,
 263 to appear in XRD diffractograms. Measurements performed in the other
 264 samples did not show relevant differences in the results. Such fact is in
 265 accordance with the XRD measurements that show good crystal quality
 266 for all films. We would not expect either the presence of MoSe_2 as this
 267 phase is located in the rear of the film which is not accessible
 268 by the Raman probing volume due to the high light absorption
 269 of the Sb_2Se_3 compound [39].

271 4. Optical and Photoluminescence characterization

272 In Figure 7 is presented the reflectance spectra of the three
 273 samples grown on p-Si substrate. Si was the substrate of choice
 274 due to its well known optical properties and due to the increased
 275 flatness of the resulting layers which simplifies significantly optical
 276 interpretation due to a lesser influence of diffuse properties.
 277 The experimental results show that the percentage of reflected light
 278 varies from sample to sample. This behaviour can be attributed to
 279 the differences in the roughness and the thickness of each sample.
 280 Though, the shape of the Reflectance spectra is very similar for
 281 all the samples; presenting two reflectance edges, corresponding to
 282 an abruptly increasing of the signal, practically at the same
 283 wavelengths and that might be related with the absorption in the
 284 Sb_2Se_3 film and with silicon substrate.

285 To estimate the bandgap in which only the reflection spectra
 286 from the film side is measured, we use the approach reported
 287 by V. Kumar *et al* [40]. When the thickness is large compared
 288 with the wavelength, the absorption coefficient can be related
 289 with the reflectance by:

$$2\alpha t = \ln\left(\frac{R_{max} - R_{min}}{R - R_{min}}\right) \quad (1)$$

286 where t is the film's thickness, R_{max} and R_{min} are the maximum
 287 and the minimum Reflectance in the reflection spectra, respectively
 288 and R the reflectance at a given energy ($h\nu$), being h and
 289 ν the Planck's constant and the frequency, respectively.

Figure 6: Results of the Raman scattering characterization of the sample selenized at $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a SLG substrate. Two different spots are shown a) stoichiometric composition where Sb_2Se_3 raman modes are present with the main peaks at 150 and 188 cm^{-1} and b) Se-rich region with additional rhombohedral Se peak signatures according to ref. [34, 37]

It is well known that the absorption coefficient is proportional to $\propto (h\nu - E_g)^{0.5}$ for a direct gap material and $\propto (h\nu - E_g)^2$ for an indirect gap material [41]. Thus, plotting $[\ln(\frac{R_{max} - R_{min}}{R - R_{min}})]^2$ versus $h\nu$ is possible by using Tauc's method to estimate the direct E_g . In a similar way, plotting $[\ln(\frac{R_{max} - R_{min}}{R - R_{min}})]^{0.5}$ versus $h\nu$ allows extracting the indirect E_g .

Both plots were tested and the results have shown that within Sb_2Se_3 absorption spectral range the direct band gap are well fitted by a straight line as illustrated in Fig. 8 for sample selenized at $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The Tauc's plots yield to a direct band gap of $1.06 \pm 0.01\text{ eV}$ for this sample. The value obtained is close to the bulk value previously reported [42]. Similar values are extracted for samples selenized at higher temperatures, $1.06 \pm 0.03\text{ eV}$ and $1.06 \pm 0.06\text{ eV}$, for $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. This analysis led to the same value of the band gap energy for the three samples grown on Si, which agrees with the close stoichiometry values obtained for these samples. Such fact is also in agreement with the XRD and Raman measurements that show both good crystalline quality and the presence of the Sb_2Se_3 phase. It should also be noted that a bandgap around 1 eV , although not ideal, is a value that is compatible with efficient solar cells.

The inset graph of Fig. 8 shows the Tauc's plot for the indirect band gap within silicon's absorption spectral range of Si substrate of sample processed at $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. As expected, the data are well fitted by a straight line, yielding to an indirect gap of

Figure 7: Room Temperature Reflectance spectra of Sb_2Se_3 films grown on p-Si substrate.

Figure 8: Room Temperature energy band gap of Sb_2Se_3 film for the sample selenized at $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ grown on a p-Si substrate. The inset graph shows the Tauc's plot for the indirect band gap of Si substrate.

1.09 \pm 0.01 eV. This value is lower than the value of 1.12 eV (300 K), commonly reported for intrinsic bulk silicon [43]. We consider that this difference is a consequence of the band gap narrowing due to the p doping [44, 45] of the Si substrate used.

Figure 9 shows the PL spectra measured at 7 K for the three samples with Si substrates. For all spectra, sharp radiative transitions related with the Si substrate (p-type) are observed, and correspond to free and bound excitons recombinations involving one (TO) or two (TO+O^Γ) phonons [46]. An identified sharp line at 1.06 eV is also commonly observed in Si [47]. For samples selenized at $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the luminescence is dominated by a broad and asymmetric band with peak energy at ~ 0.85 eV and a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of ~ 100 meV. A shoulder at ~ 0.75 eV is observed. In the case of sample selenized at $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, this shoulder dominates the spectrum. We note that the relative intensity of the band at ~ 0.85 eV decreases with the increase of the selenization temperature. This behaviour with the large FWHM suggests a possible relation with defects. On the other hand, the relative intensity of the band at ~ 0.75 eV increases significantly for selenization process at the highest temperature, which could reflect a better crystalline quality in that film. Additionally, it is

Max. Selenization temp.	$300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	$400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
$p(\times 10^{13}\text{ cm}^{-3})$	9	570	100
$\mu(\text{cm}^2\text{v}^{-1}\text{ s}^{-1})$	4.5	0.7	4.8
$\rho(\Omega\text{cm})$	15381	1635	1290
$N_A(\times 10^{15}\text{ cm}^{-3})$	—	1	25

Table 3: Free hole concentration, p , mobility, μ and resistivity ρ measured at 400 K, for the samples deposited in SLG substrates.

observed a decrease of the relative intensity of the Si related sharp lines with the increase of the growth temperature which can be related with a higher thickness of the film and, consequently, a higher absorption of the incident photons in the film. Furthermore, we note that the emissions are in agreement with the estimated bandgap of the films as the luminescence must come from energy values lower than the materials bandgap. The observation of luminescent is quite important as it is a good indication of good properties relevant to solar cell devices.

Figure 9: PL spectra measured at 7 K for samples with Si substrate selenized at $300\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $350\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, under an excitation of 200 mW. The observed sharp lines are related with the Si substrate. The sharp line at 1.06 eV is an unidentified transition in Si.

5. Electrical characterization

The free hole concentration, p , mobility, μ , and resistivity, ρ , measured at 400 K, for the samples deposited in SLG substrates are reported in table 3. As mentioned, for these measurements, non conductive substrates are needed and SLG were chosen due to its insulating nature.

As shown from these measurements, all samples present low values of carrier concentration and mobility. However, there are not clear correlations between annealing temperature and electrical transport parameters apart from an increase in the free hole concentration by almost two orders of magnitude.

Figure 10 shows the electrical resistivity and all three samples show an Arrhenius behaviour at high temperatures with the same activation energy of 0.5 eV. While in the sample annealed at $400\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ this behaviour appears in the 400 K – 250 K range, for the lowest annealing temperature samples that range is extended to 170 K. According to the literature and considering a

slow variation of the free carrier mobility with temperature, the activation energy of the resistivity in this region should correspond to $Eg/2$ [48], confirming the values of $Eg \approx 1$ eV above reported. Similar results were already reported for Sb_2Se_3 thin films prepared by thermal evaporation [49] and rapid thermal evaporation [6].

Figure 10: Electrical resistivity as a function of the reciprocal temperatures for the samples with SLG substrates annealing at 300 °C, 350 °C and 400 °C.

At lower temperatures the slope of the resistivity curve strongly decreases, for the samples annealed at 350 °C and 400 °C, to an activation energy of a few meV. A similar behaviour was also observed for Sb_2Se_3 thin films prepared by rapid thermal evaporation [6]. In reference [6] the resistivity activation energy in this temperature range is associated to shallow acceptors (Se_{Sb}) and Mott variable range hopping ($\rho \approx \exp[(T_0/T)^{1/4}]$) [50–52]. However, the Arrhenius dependency and low activation energy in our samples indicate that the electronic transport in this temperature range is due to nearest-neighbour hopping (NNH) [51, 52]:

$$\rho_{NNH} = \rho_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{E_A}{k_B T}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$E_A = 0.99 \cdot e^2 \cdot \frac{N_A^{1/3}}{4\pi\epsilon} \quad (3)$$

where ρ_{NNH} is the resistivity of the sample due to NNH, ρ_0 is a constant, N_A is the acceptor concentration, E_A is the activation energy for hole hopping and ϵ is the dielectric permittivity of Sb_2Se_3 . By fitting the experimental data with eq. 2 and using eq. 3 the acceptor concentration in the samples annealed at 350 °C and 400 °C was found and reported in Table 3. Such values of N_A allow for the fabrication of devices like diodes and solar cells. However, depending on the band alignment, higher values of N_A would be required in order to obtain high built-in voltages that allow for high values of open circuit voltages in solar cells. Such increase of doping in chalcopyrite materials is usually obtained by adding alkali elements that change the compensation ratio [28].

6. Conclusion

In this work, it is shown that a RF magnetron sputtering and subsequent selenization process is suitable to grow Sb_2Se_3 films with good crystal and optoelectronic quality. Some compositional and morphological differences are observed when comparing the films grown in SLG, SLG/Mo and Si substrates. The latter gives compositions close to stoichiometry and more regular grains with increasing selenization temperatures. As expected, a general increase in grain size is observed for all substrates with increasing values of selenization temperature. XRD results show that with this growth method no columnar orientation is observed. Raman scattering detected localized presence of rhombohedral and amorphous Se, which is consistent with the composition EDS measurements and condensation of Se during the cool down of the selenization process. Optical measurements done on the samples with Si substrates allowed us to extract a direct bandgap close to 1.06 eV for the tested selenization temperatures. Photoluminescence performed in the same samples present a dominant, broad shoulder at 0.85 eV for samples selenized at 300 °C and 350 °C and, a sharper and intense peak close to 0.75 eV for the sample selenized at 400 °C. A intense peak with an energy close to the bandgap value is a relevant feature in materials for application in solar cells. Electrical characterization of the samples grown on SLG substrates show low free hole concentrations and low mobilities. The study indicates that for low temperature regime the electronic transport is due to nearest-neighbour hopping. The low values obtained for acceptor concentrations pointed out that doping and compensation issues should be addressed in future work.

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